

BIOLOGICAL VALUE OF THE PROTEINS OF SOME SPECIES OF BENGAL FISH BY THE NITROGEN BALANCE AND GROWTH METHODS.

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The biological value of the proteins of some common species of Bengal fish, *viz.*, *Katla* (*Catla catla*), *Mrigel* (*Cirrhina mrigala*), *Air* (*Arius arius*), *Koi* (*Anabas Testudineus*), *Singhi* (*Saccobranchus Fossilis*), *Sarputi*, *Poa* and *Koral* has been determined by the nitrogen balance as well as by the growth methods. The digestibility and biological value of the fish proteins are in general very high. The digestibility varies between 83 and 97% cent. and the biological value between 70 and 88%. A growth per g. of proteins ingested varies from 1.48 to 1.83 per day.

Fish constitutes an important part of the dietary in Bengal and in view of the fact that the nutritive value of proteins of pulses, an important source of proteins for Indians, is not very high, the determination of the biological values of the proteins of Bengal fish, which are taken almost daily in moderate amounts, is a very important problem. The biological values of the proteins of two very common varieties of Bengal fish, the *Labeo rohita* (*ruhee*) and the *Clupea ilisa* (*hilsa*) were previously determined in this laboratory (Basu and De, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1938, 25, 177).

In the present paper the biological values of several other common species of Bengal fish have been investigated both by the balance sheet and growth methods.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Composition and the Preparation of Fish and Fish meal.—The head, tail, scales and bones of the fish were rejected. The fish was cut into thin slices and put in the steam oven. When the slices were dry, they were chopped in a small chopper and finally dried in the sun.

In the case of fish without scales (except *Singhi*) the outer deposit of fat was also rejected.

The following is the list of the different varieties of fish with their scientific and Bengali names and the percentages of protein, fat and moisture in the whole fish and in the dried meal. The percentage of proteins in the whole fish generally varies between 16 and 21, that

of moisture between 68 and 75 and that of fat between 0.4 and 3.4 excepting *Koi* which contains 8.8% fat and 14.8% protein.

Bengali names.	Scientific names.	Fish meals.			Whole fish.		
		Crude protein.	Ether extract.	Moisture.	Crude protein.	Fat	Water.
Katla	<i>Catla catla</i>	73.5%	12.27%	7.2%	19.2%	2.5%	70%
Mrigal	<i>Cirrhina mrigala</i>	78.36	4.02	7.46	19.6	1.0	74
Air	<i>Artus arius</i>	77.85	10.88	4.9	20.5	2.2	68
Koi	<i>Anabas testudineus</i>	61.79	28.59	3.16	14.6	8.8	71
Singhi	<i>Saccobranchus fossilis</i> .	81.44	7.04	6.88	16.0	1.1	76
Sarputi	...	70.7	18.11	5.84	17.5	2.0	74
Poa	...	75.42	10.55	5.77	18.6	1.7	75
Koral	...	92.98	1.42	3.11	21.0	1.5	72

Composition of the Diet.—The nitrogen-free diets were of the same composition as those used by previous workers in this laboratory (*loc. cit.*).

The diets containing the fish proteins were prepared by replacing the necessary amounts of starch in the nitrogen-free diet to the fish meals, which had been previously freed from fat.

Balance Sheet Method.—The technique was the same as that followed by the previous workers in this laboratory (Basu, Nath and Ghani, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1936, 23, 789, 811; Basu, Nath and Mukherjee, *ibid.*, 1937, 24, 1001; Basu and De, *ibid.*, 1938, 26, 177).

Typical data of the balance sheet method are given in Tables I and II. The results are summarised in Table III.

TABLE I.

Experiment with nitrogen-free ration.

(Figures of intake and excretion represent daily averages).

Rat No.	Average weight.	Food intake.	Urinary N.	Faecal nitrogen.	
				Total.	per g. of food intake.
506	232 g.	9.2 g.	49.9 mg.	19.6 mg.	2.13 mg.
507	224.5	9.9	58.9	11.9	1.2
508	227	9.9	46.1	13.38	1.35
509	219	10.0	49.6	24.2	2.42
510	222.5	9.25	48.9	21.5	2.32
511	235.5	8.4	45.3	15.1	1.80

TABLE II.
Biological value of Katla fish protein (10% level).

(Figures of intakes and excretion represent daily averages).

Rat No.	Average Food. body weight.	Intake		Faecal nitrogen		Food N absorbed.		Urinary nitrogen		Food N utilised.	B.V.	Mean B. V.	D.
		Food.	Nitrogen.	Total.	Exo.	Total.	Exo.	Total.	Exo.				
506	218 g.	9'73g.	148'2 mg.	41'03 mg.	20'72 mg.	20'31 mg.	127'89 mg.	78'44 mg.	49'9 mg.	28'54 mg.	99'35 mg.	77'68	86'29
507	215'5	9'08	138'4	28'46	10'9	17'56	120'84	88'82	58'9	29'92	90'92	75'24	87'1
508	223	10'55	160'7	37'04	14'24	22'80	137'9	76'24	46'1	30'14	107'76	78'14	85'81
509	210'5	10'0	152'4	47'92	24'2	23'72	128'68	75'04	49'6	25'44	103'24	80'23	84'44
510	208'5	9'25	141'0	37'72	21'46	16'26	124'74	78'43	48'9	29'53	95'21	76'33	88'47
511	226'5	11'35	173'0	43'64	20'44	23'20	149'89	75'32	45'3	30'02	119'87	80'11	86'6

77'96

TABLE III.

Biological value (B.V.) and digestibility (D) of the proteins of some Bengal fish (at 10% level).

Rat No.	Average body wt.	Katla		Mrigel		Air		Sarputi	
		B.V.	D.	B.V.	D.	B.V.	D.	B.V.	D.
501	225 g.					76.28	93.52	85.24	97.19
502	208					75.06	95.43	80.48	95.33
503	210.5					72.65	96.33	81.07	93.94
504	221					74.05	93.22	83.72	96.47
505	222.5					74.8	92.12	80.11	98.02
506	232	77.68	86.29			73.97	95.30	83.87	96.77
507	224.5	75.24	87.1						
508	227	78.14	85.81						
509	219	80.23	84.44						
510	222.5	76.33	88.47						
511	235.5	80.11	86.6						
512	234								
513	243.5			72.1	92.8				
514	241.5			74.24	89.84				
515	226.5			70.57	92.44				
516	236			69.55	90.36				
517	214			71.49	94.42				
518	216.5			74.79	94.32				
Average.		77.96	86.45	72.12	92.36	74.47	94.32	82.42	96.29

Rat No.	Average body wt.	Koi		Singh		Poa		Koral	
		B.V.	D.	B.V.	D.	B.V.	D.	B.V.	D.
501	225 g.					76.05	96.54	80.5	98.5
502	208					74.94	97.66	85.22	95.23
503	210.5					77.2	94.5	83.6	95.7
504	221					75.51	97.21	82.95	96.18
505	222.5					75.3	93.4		
506	232								
507	224.5	84.24	93.74						
508	227	88.17	92.82						
509	219	85.65	97.55						
510	222.5	88.3	95.4						
511	235.5	84.9	97.86						
512	234	89.78	97.43						
513	243.5			91.6	97.1				
514	241.5			85.64	96.35				
515	226.5			86.72	93.27				
516	236			87.5	97.05				
517	214			90.81	93.2			85.8	97.72
518	216.5			88.43	95.82			81.81	98.1
Average.		86.84	95.6	88.45	95.47	75.8	95.86	83.3	97.07

TABLE IV.

Biological value of proteins of fish by growth method (at 15 per cent level).

Material.	No. of rats.	Period of expt. weeks.	Increase in wt.		Total food intake		Protein intake (Mean).	B.V. = $\frac{\text{Gain in wt.}}{\text{Protein intake}}$
			Variation.	Mean.	Variation.	Mean.		
Katla (<i>Catla catla</i>)	6	{ 4 { 8	71.5-88.5 g.	79.3 g.	227.4-252.4 g.	240.4 g.	36.06 g.	2.20
			106-132	119.1	368.8-504.2	437.4	65.61	1.83
Air (<i>Arius arius</i>)	6	{ 4 { 8	55.5-89.5	70.0	174.6-286.8	237.2	35.58	1.97
			82.5-125	105.7	305.6-478.9	420.8	63.12	1.67
Mrigel (<i>Cirrhina mrigala</i>)	5	{ 4 { 8	50-62	55.9	168.2-196.8	182.8	27.42	2.04
			67-94.5	80.7	259.8-359.9	310.6	46.5	1.73
Singhi (<i>Saccobranches fossilis</i>)	6	{ 4 { 8	45-63.5	50.8	171.4-220.5	183.5	27.52	1.84
			61.5-92.5	74.5	297.1-385.4	233.6	35.04	1.48

Growth Method.—The biological value of proteins of four fish (*Katla Air, Mrigel* and *Singhi*) was determined by this method, the technique employed being the same as that used by previous workers in this laboratory (*loc. cit.*). The results are given in Table IV.

D I S C U S S I O N.

In the following table the biological value, digestibility at 10% protein level and also the growths induced in young rats per g. of protein intake at 15% level of different fish proteins have been collected.

TABLE V.

Fish (Bengali name).	Scientific name.	Digestibility.	Biological value at 10% level.	Growth per g. of protein intake at 15% level per day.
Katla	<i>Catla catla</i>	86·45	77·96	1·83
Mrigel	<i>Cirrhina mrigala</i>	92·38	72·12	1·73
Air	<i>Arius arius</i>	94·32	74·47	1·67
Sarputi		96·29	82·42	...
Koi	<i>Anabas testudineus</i>	95·6	86·84	...
Singhi	<i>Saccobranchus fossilis</i>	95·47	88·45	1·48
Poa	...	95·86	75·8	...
Koral	...	97·07	83·3	...
Ruhee	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	88·6	78·9	1·71
Hilsa	<i>Clupea illisa</i>	82·6	69·5	1·48

It would appear from the above that except in the case of *Hilsa*, the digestibility and biological value of the fish proteins are very high. The small fishes *Koi* and *Singhi* possess very high biological values and these species are also recommended for invalids in our country. The growth-promoting qualities of the *Singhi* are, however, not as good as those of the *Ruhee*, *Katla*, *Mrigel* and *Air*. The *Hilsa* also possesses comparatively poor growth-promoting properties.

The different fishes contain a large percentage of proteins of very good quality and their consumption as a daily article of food by the Bengalees is a very good habit.